

TAX IMPROVEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *In this article, the methods and global experiences of the fundamental improvement of tax administration in the conditions of the digital economy, the collection of taxes and other mandatory payments are highlighted. It is of particular importance to develop a strategy for improving tax administration, which includes the following goals, tasks and main directions. Improvement of the tax administration and liberalization of liability for violations of the law played an important role in improving the business environment.*

Keywords. *Tax system, economy, investment, production, finance, tax administration, tax burden, business, business activity.*

The modern tax system is one of the main conditions for the rapid development of the economy, creation of favorable conditions for business activities, improvement of the investment environment, expansion of production and provision of services. In the "Strategy of Development" for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, the issues of simplifying the tax administration and reducing the tax burden by expanding the tax base have a special place. Over the past years, necessary measures have been taken in order to reduce inspections of business entities and stop unjustified interference in their business activities.

Procedures for unscheduled and alternative audits of business entities have been canceled, the form and terms of submission of tax reports submitted by entrepreneurs have been simplified.

At the same time, due to the existence of a number of problems in the implementation of the tax administration system, the following important directions for the reform of the system of state tax service bodies were determined:

- ❖ wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies and advanced automated analysis methods into the process of tax administration, to provide direct electronic services to taxpayers, first of all, to business entities without communication straight pass;

- ❖ responsibility to ensure timely and reliable accounting of taxation objects and the taxable base, to provide reliable information related to taxation issues of authorized bodies and organizations in a timely manner increase;

- ❖ providing all-round assistance to taxpayers in fulfilling their tax obligations, developing effective tax mechanisms for the prevention of tax offenses and increasing the legal culture of taxpayers, introducing modern methods of tax control;

- ❖ implementation of effective measures to ensure the full coverage of taxation objects and the expansion of the tax base through a systematic analysis of the dynamics of macroeconomic indicators and the tax potential of the regions;

- ❖ all-round assistance to restore the activities of non-performing enterprises, to improve the financial condition of low-profit and loss-making enterprises, to strengthen the mechanisms of mutual settlements, and to prevent tax debt from increasing expanding the base;

- ❖ further expansion of cooperation with financial authorities, interested ministries and agencies, as well as local state authorities by determining taxation issues, including additional reserves for increasing the revenues of the republican and local budgets;

❖ carrying out systematic work on the selection and placement of personnel, filling tax authorities with qualified employees with high moral and ethical qualities, as well as ensuring the prevention of offenses among employees and providing services for them to create suitable conditions for.

In addition, in order to ensure "healthy competition" between business entities and to end "secret business": control-cash machines that provide online information about calculations to tax authorities an automated cash receipt control system is being introduced. In addition, in order to legalize real jobs, the state tax service authorities are tasked with systematic monitoring of the compliance of the reported and actual number of employees of economic entities.

As a result of the implementation of the concept of improving the tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tax burden on the labor compensation fund was reduced, taxes on working capital were optimized, mandatory allocations to state special funds were canceled and the profit tax rate on legal entities was reduced. the tax system was revised by reducing it.

At the same time, the tax system has the following shortcomings and problems that prevent the increase of business and investment activity, the formation of a healthy competitive environment, as well as the effective implementation of tax reforms:

✓ firstly, the principles of organization of tax administration are outdated and do not provide comprehensive services to taxpayers, as well as voluntary fulfillment of tax obligations by them;

✓ secondly, the level of administrative costs (time and money spent) in fulfilling tax obligations remains high;

✓ thirdly, there are no clear criteria and mechanisms for granting tax incentives;

✓ -fourthly, mechanisms of public control aimed at reducing the level of the secret economy, as well as encouraging processes of legalization of business activities, are not perfect;

✓ fifthly, there are no uniform standards and software products that ensure the exchange of information between the taxpayer and the tax authorities;

✓ -sixth, interdepartmental information cooperation, which reduces the quality of tax accounting, prevents the expansion of the tax base and the provision of stable tax revenues, is slow;

✓ -seventh, there are systemic deficiencies in the field of training of highly qualified personnel and in the evaluation of the activities of tax authorities.

These shortcomings and problems prevent the rapid development of the tax system, the improvement of the efficiency of the tax administration, and the collection of taxes and compulsory payments at the required level. In this regard, it is of particular importance to develop a strategy for improving tax administration, which includes the following goals, tasks and main directions. Improvement of the tax administration and liberalization of liability for violations of the law played an important role in improving the business environment.

Therefore, reforms aimed at creating a fair, transparent and long-term system in this regard are currently being implemented in our country. As a result, a completely new tax administration is emerging. Entrepreneurs feel the practical effect and result of this not in beautiful words as before, but in their daily activities.

Today, according to the reduction of the types of taxes and their rates, first of all, the types of taxes are reduced from 16 to 9, the forms of control are reduced from 13 to 2. 3.2 percent fees were canceled. About 7,000 enterprises have been exempted from paying an average of 6 trillion in taxes annually due to the cancellation of these fees for extra-budgetary funds. So, they will keep that much money. Also, property, income and social tax rates were reduced by 2 times. If we express this through specific examples, the tax burden in the transport sector has

decreased by 3 times, in the food industry by 2 times, and in the textile and electrical engineering industry by 20 percent.

At this point, it is necessary to clarify one more issue. Last year, after the implementation of the new tax code, the participants of 23 special economic zones addressed the President with the question whether our previous privileges will be preserved or not. According to these questions, the entrepreneurs who registered in the economic zones from February 2020 until the adoption of the law on special economic zones were given guarantees that the benefits would be preserved. According to the current law, these entrepreneurs are exempted from property, land and water taxes for up to 10 years based on the amount of investment. Now the profit tax will be added to these benefits, and about 300 billion soums per year will remain at the disposal of enterprises.

In conclusion, since the first days of our country's independence, effective reforms have been carried out to improve the tax administration, create favorable conditions for the development of entrepreneurship on a large scale in our society. It is noteworthy that a number of regulatory documents, laws, and legal documents related to business activities have been adopted, and their legal guarantees are being strengthened more and more.

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